

Concept “Wealth” in the System of English Proverbs

Saparova Intizor Pulatjanovna¹

¹ An English teacher of the Urgench state university, Uzbekistan

Abstract:

This scientific article devoted to the study of the concept “wealth” in the system of English proverbs. Wealth is the abundance of valuable financial assets or physical possessions, which can be converted into a form that can be used for transactions. Proverbs allows us to join the way of thinking of another people, understand the originality of the national character, the value system of a certain ethnic group.

Keywords: concept, wealth, proverbs, abundance of valuable financial assets, physical possessions, ethnic group.

In modern linguistics, one of the significant issues is the study of concepts. Modern scientists consider language in its connection with human thinking and spiritual culture, which causes the relevance of studying this issue. From the standpoint of linguoculturology, the concept is presented as a mass of culture in the human mind, in the form of which culture enters the mental world of a person; the relationship between language and culture manifests itself in ways of linguistic explication of ethnic mentality [3, p. 7; 2, p. 12].

In the proverbs, considered in this study in its narrower meaning, as proverbs and sayings, the labor, moral and aesthetic experience of the people, compressed into wise sayings, is reflected. Proverbs allows us to join the way of thinking of another people, understand the originality of the national character, the value system of a certain ethnic group.

Proverbs contain a frozen comprehension of a particular concept that has developed over a long time and has changed depending on time and place, the conditions of manifestations of conceptual entities in the life of the people, individual groups of people, an individual [4, p. 63].

In this article we discuss proverbs and sayings with the concept of «wealth» in English.

Concept «*wealth*» is expressed by the lexeme «wealth». According to the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English, the lexeme «*wealth*» is understood as follows:

«1. 1 (a) a large amount of money, some property, etc.;

1. life in abundance;

2. a large amount or amount of something » [5].

Synonyms for this lexeme in English are *money, riches, means, fortune, prosperity, plenty, purse, of which wealth, money, plenty, purse* were found in proverbs. Moreover, *money* is most common.

Let's look at how «*wealth*» is reflected in the proverbs of the English language. For representatives of the English ethnic group, the presence of wealth is important, this is reflected in proverbs indicating the power and power of money. The identified proverbs indicate that *wealth* – is power and power to which everything obeys:

Examples:

Money makes the world go around. /Money makes the earth spin around its axis.

Money is power. /Money is power.

Money is the god of the world / Money – deity for the world

A heavy purse makes a light heart. /The tightly stuffed wallet makes your heart easy.

A light purse makes a heavy heart. /Pul barcha eshiklarni ochadi.

For the English mentality, wealth is never in abundance, and there is no specific maximum size for it. The omnipotence of money and wealth, according to the British, can even buy love.

Examples:

Money makes marriage. /Money creates marriages.

Love lasts as long as money endures. /Love is as long as there is money

Who marries for love without money, has good nights and sorry days. /Whoever marries for love, but without money, has joyful but sad days.

At the same time, in language one can observe proverbs and sayings in which wealth receives a negative assessment. A person can become a slave to money:

Examples:

A great fortune is a great glory. /Great fortune – big slavery.

Wealth, according to some proverbs, is the real evil that destroys youth and health:

Money is the root of all evil. /Money – root of all evil

When riches increase, the body decreases /We accumulate wealth, but ruin our health.

An abundance of money ruins youth. /The abundance of money destroys youth.

These proverbs claim that wealth subjugates a person, depriving him of freedom, health and even youth.

Cash is king.

Modern saying, summarizing the position in a recession.

Bad money drives out good.

Money of lower intrinsic value tends to circulate more freely than money of higher intrinsic and equal nominal value, though what is recognized as money of higher value being hoarded; English proverb, early 20th century; known as ‘Gresham’s law’ from Thomas Gresham, English financier and founder of the Royal Exchange.

The best things in life are free.

English proverb, early 20th century, originally from the title of a song (1927) by Buddy De Sylva and Lew Brown.

LODP Get the money honestly if you can.

American proverb, early 19th century; the idea is found in the classical world, in the poetry of Horace (65–8 BC), ‘If possible honestly, if not, somehow, make money.

He that cannot pay, let him pray.

If you have no material resources, prayer is your only resort; English proverb, early 17th century.

Money can’t buy happiness.

English proverb, mid 19th century.

Money has no smell.

English proverb, early 20th century in this form, but originally deriving from a comment made by the Roman Emperor Vespasian (AD 9–79), in response to an objection to a tax on public lavatories; compare Where there’s muck there’s brass below.

Money is like sea water. The more you drink, the thirstier you become.

Possession of wealth creates an addiction to money; modern saying.

Money isn’t everything.

Often said in consolation or resignation; English proverbs, early 20th century.

Money is power.

English proverb, mid 18th century.

Money is the root of all evil.

English proverb, mid 15th century, deriving from the Bible, “The love of money is the root of all evil”.

Money, like manure, does no good till it is spread.

English proverbs, early 19th century; the idea is found earlier in the Essays of Francis Bacon, “Money is like muck, not good except it be spread”.

Money makes the mare to go.

Referring to money as a source of power; English proverb, late 15th century.

Money talks.

Money has influence; English proverb, mid 17th century.

A penny for the guy.

Traditional saying, used by children displaying a guy to ask for money towards celebrating Bonfire Night; a guy is an effigy representing Guy Fawkes, a leading conspirator in the Gunpowder Plot to

blow up James I and his Parliament in 1605, which is traditionally burned on the 5th of November, the anniversary of the discovery of the plot.

Shrouds have no pockets.

Worldly wealth cannot be kept and used after death; English proverb, mid 19th century.

Time is money.

Moreover, the larger the amount of wealth, the greater the dependence on it and the underlying.

What is also noteworthy is the relationship between generally recognized human values and wealth.

According to some proverbs, *wealth* and *money* can replace such a universal value for a person as friendship, that is, by gaining financial independence, a person is removed from society as a whole.

For example:

He that has a full purse never wanted a friend/He who has a full wallet does not need friends.

However, health is above all material benefits for the British. The following examples suggest that good health is more valuable than money and cannot be bought for any wealth:

Health surpasses riches. /Health is more valuable than wealth.

Good health is above wealth. /Health is more valuable than money.

Health is better than wealth. /Health – the first wealth.

Wealth is nothing without health. /Wealth without health – nothing.

Having analyzed fund of the proverbs of English, we can conclude that there is an uncertain attitude towards the *wealth* of the English ethnic group.

In general, *wealth* is assessed positively; it is believed that without wealth you cannot succeed in society, and even in love. However, *wealth* in relation, for example, to health depreciates, losing its significance and power.

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